

COMPARATIVE-TYPOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF NOUN-PHRASES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Annotation: this article aims to analyze and compare noun phrases in both English and Uzbek languages by the help of several examples in both languages.

Key words: noun phrase, verb phrase, adjective phrases, and adverbial phrases, word combinations

Аннотация: эта статья направлена на анализ и сравнение именных словосочетаний на английском и узбекском языках с помощью нескольких примеров на обоих языках.

Ключевые слова: именное словосочетание, глагольное словосочетание, прилагательное и наречное словосочетание, словосочетание

Languages are different in several aspects, including grammar, pronunciation, syntax, and vocabulary. However, the analysis of word combination phrases in various languages, such as English and Uzbek, reveals similarities and differences. Word combinations or phrases represent a critical structure in languages and are used to convey a message.

English and Uzbek languages have several similarities regarding word combination phrases. For example, both languages use noun phrases, verb phrases, adjective phrases, and adverbial phrases. A noun phrase is a combination of a noun and other words such as adjectives, articles, and determiners to provide more

information about the noun. In English, a noun phrase can be, “*the blue sea*” while in Uzbek, it can be “*moviy dengiz*” For example, *Bolakay moviy dengizga tikilib o'tirardi.* (Ch.Aytmatov ,Oq kema) (in English :*A boy was sitting staring at the blue sea*).

A verb phrase, on the other hand, is a combination of a verb and other words such as adverbs, objects, and complements to convey an action. In English, a verb phrase can be, “*to play football,*” while in Uzbek, it can be “*futbol o'ynamoq.*”

In addition, both English and Uzbek languages use adjective phrases to provide more information about a noun. An adjective phrase is a combination of an adjective and other words such as adverbs and intensifiers. In English, an adjective phrase can be, “*very beautiful,*” while in Uzbek, it can be “*juda chiroyli.*” (“*Juda qiziq, juda chiroyli*” Quddus Muhammadiy). An adverbial phrase, on the other hand, is a combination of an adverb and other words such as prepositions and articles to give more information about a verb. In English, an adverbial phrase can be, “*in the morning*” while in Uzbek, it can be “*ertalab.*” “*Ertalab ko'z ochgan odam kechgacha yashaydimi yo'qmi bilmaydi?*” (Xolid Husayniy “Shamollar ortidan yugurib”)

However, there are also differences between English and Uzbek regarding word combination phrases. Firstly, Uzbek has more complex inflections compared to English. Inflections convey grammatical information, such as tense, case, and person. For example, in English, there are only three tenses (past, present, and future), while Uzbek has several more (past indefinite, present continuous, etc.). These inflections affect word combinations differently in the two languages.

Secondly, Uzbek allows postpositions to form word combination phrases, while English uses prepositions. Postpositions are particles that come after a noun or pronoun and indicate its relationship with the rest of the sentence. For example, in Uzbek, “*kitobning ustida*” means “*on the book,*” while in English, it would be “*on top of the book.*”

In conclusion, word combination phrases are a critical part of languages, and their analysis reveals similarities and differences between them. While English and Uzbek both use noun phrases, verb phrases, adjective phrases, and adverbial phrases, they differ regarding inflections and the use of postpositions or prepositions. By understanding these differences, speakers of both languages can communicate more effectively and accurately in both languages.

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